

DGIP-CEDS

Data Governance and Intellectual Property Governance
in Common European Data Spaces

PrAVri

Pravni fakultet u Rijeci

Driving the Data Economy: How the Common European Mobility Data Space Can Accelerate Autonomous Vehicle Innovation Amid Legal Challenges?

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Presentation overview

Policy context (Common European Mobility Data Space)

Towards AV innovation-friendly legal solutions

How the CEMDS can accelerate AV innovation

Data-related legal challenges for the AV ecosystem

EU legal requirements for mobility / vehicle data sharing

1) Policy context (Common European Mobility Data Space)

Relevant key EU policy instruments

2020	<p><u>European Strategy for Data:</u></p> <p>“A Common European mobility data space, to position Europe at the forefront of the development of an intelligent transport system, including connected cars [.]”</p>
2020	<p><u>Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy:</u></p> <p>“[The aim is to collect, connect and make data available to meet EU objectives, from sustainability to multimodality [...]. [The CEMDS] should function in synergy with other key systems, [...] while being cyber safe and compatible with Union data protection standards. At the same time, a level playing field for data in the value chain must be preserved.”</p>
2022	<p><u>First Staff Working Document on Common European Data Spaces:</u></p> <p>“The [CEMDS] will facilitate access, pooling and sharing of data from existing and future transport and mobility databases.”</p>
2023	<p><u>Communication on Creation of a common European mobility data space:</u></p> <p>“Connected, automated and autonomous mobility – facilitating the discovery, access and sharing of infrastructure and real-time traffic data.”</p>

1) Policy context (Common European Mobility Data Space)

Unified technical, governance and legal framework for mobility data sharing across the EU

Source: [Communication on Creation of a common European mobility data space.](#)

2) How the CEMDS can accelerate AV innovation

Source: J. Laborda, E. Dani, L. Bates, J. Ahtes, R. Touma, *Unlocking the Future of Mobility with European Data Spaces*, EIT Urban Mobility, Factual Consulting, i2CAT Foundation, 2023 [boxes on AV and sustainable transportation added by author].

2) How the CEMDS can accelerate AV innovation

Improve machine learning models for AVs through diverse datasets

Pooling mobility data via CEMDS

Enable real-time data sharing for enhanced AV navigation and safety

Support data collaborations for AV R&I, testing and deployment across the EU

3) EU legal requirements for mobility / vehicle data sharing

Data protection and privacy

- General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)
- ePrivacy Directive

Open data

- Free-Flow of Non-Personal Data Regulation (FFD)
- Open Data Directive (ODD)

Cybersecurity and cyber resilience

- Cyber Resilience Act (indirectly)
- Cybersecurity Act
- NIS2 Directive
- eIDAS 2.0 Regulation

AI-specific data

- AI Act

Data governance

- Data Act
- Data Governance Act
- Interoperable Europe Act
- Platforms regulations (Digital Markets Act, Digital Services Act)

Contracts, IP protection and competition

- Private law – SCCs and MCTs
- IP law (incl. trade secrets)
- Competition law

Mobility-specific data

- Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) Directive + non-legislative acts
- Vehicle General Safety Regulation (GSR) + non-legislative acts

Note: the list is non-exhaustive.

4) Data-related legal challenges for the AV ecosystem

5) Towards AV innovation-friendly legal solutions

CLEAR POLICY INTENTION

(e.g. [Industrial Action Plan for the European automotive sector](#))

LEGAL GUIDANCES

(e.g. [Guidance on vehicle data, accompanying the Data Act](#))

REGULATORY SIMPLIFICATION

(Digital omnibus package and continuous sector-specific reviews needed)

TRUST

(creation of multistakeholder data ecosystems and mutually beneficial legal mechanisms needed for AV R&I, testing and deployment)

Thank you for your attention!

For questions and potential collaborations:

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Project website:

<https://pravri.uniri.hr/en/project/dgip-ceds/>